

Figure S1: Number distributions inside the perturbed (top) and control (bottom) chamber at different times after turning on UV lights ($t=0$ h) for Exp. B1.

Figure S2: Simulated and measured particle number distributions after the UV lights were turned on in the perturbed chamber for Exp. A1.

Figure S3: Comparison of nucleation rate ($J_{1.7}$) with measurements of ambient observations and with laboratory experiments (CLOUD campaign) as a function of $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ (Kirkby et al. 2011 and references therein).